

Solid phase extraction of arsenic for the enrichment from aqueous environment using a modified cellulose surface

Mitali Sarkar* and Kingshuk Ghosh,

Department of Chemistry, University of Kalyani, Kalyani-741 235, West Bengal, India

E-mail : mitali_ku@yahoo.com

Manuscript received 22 June 2010, accepted 16 August 2010

Abstract : Iron loaded cellulose is found to have the potential to act as a solid phase extractant for the removal and enrichment of arsenic from aqueous environment. The equilibrium is found to attain at 135 min. The process is found to be influenced by the pH of the solution and the extent of extraction depends on the initial arsenic concentration as well the solution temperature. The role of different foreign anions influencing the extraction extent is determined. Of the different isotherm tested the equilibrium data is best fitted to the three parameters Sips model rather than the two parameters Langmuir and Freundlich models. The goodness of data fit was evaluated through regression coefficient, standard error of estimate and chi square parameters. The process is aided by negative free energy, positive enthalpy and positive entropy change. The applicability of the process in sample solution is tested through an off-line SPE-AAS/CV combination.

Keywords : Arsenic, enrichment, solid phase extraction, modified cellulose.

Introduction

Trace level determination of arsenic from various matrices becomes an important and challenging task for the analytical chemists today. Enrichment of trace constituent constitutes the first step of any analytical determinations. Among the different enrichment techniques solid phase extraction has main advantages of high capacity, short time, easy operation and amenable to automation¹. Literature reports on SPE of arsenic includes use of ion exchange resin, modified silica and alumina, carbon nano tubes as well as some biomaterial like eggshell membrane and waste material like fly ash².

The aim of the present communication is to develop an analytical method for the extraction of arsenic(V) by using cellulose supported metal oxide (CMO), a solid phase extractant as well as to enrich arsenic(V) from water samples. Cellulose as the substrate for the extractant is a cheap, green and easily available natural linear chain polymer³ comprising of repeating β -D-glucopyranose units covalently linked through acetal functions between the OH group of the C4 and C1 carbon atoms (β -1,4-glucan). Generally, cellulose moiety is modified following chemical routes viz. esterification, halogenation, oxidation,

etherification etc. as well as the grafting to remove metal ions⁴. The methods require strict control of reaction conditions, use of costly chemicals and are therefore both cost and energy intensive.

The present study describes a simple route for iron loaded cellulose as the solid phase extractant for arsenic removal via enrichment/preconcentration. The thermodynamic efficiency of the operation and applicability in monitoring arsenic in aqueous environmental sample is tested with an off-line SPE coupled with AAS/CV.

Results and discussion

The prepared substrate is characterized through XRD and SEM analysis. Successful and cost-effective removal of solutes from water by adsorption requires an optimal unit operation. The design parameters need to be first be optimised in a batch equilibrium mode. The parameters tested are the initial arsenic concentration, shaking time and speed, solution pH and temperature, dose and particle size of the adsorbent. The extent of adsorption is found to increase with increase in shaking time, shaking speed, solution temperature and the dose of the adsorbent. The equilibrium time is found to be 135 min for

adsorbent of particle size $< 53 \mu\text{m}$ at a dose 4.0 g dm^{-3} and a shaking speed of 400 rpm. The influence of pH on the adsorption behavior is illustrated in Fig. 1. The percent adsorption of As^{V} increases with solution pH and was maximum in the pH range 4.8 to 7.1. With further

Fig. 1. Extent of extraction with pH variation.

increase of pH the extent of adsorption was found to decrease. The pH dependent adsorption behavior can be explained in terms of arsenic speciation in solution and the charge of the adsorbent surface. At the pH value below the zero point charge (pH_{ZPC}) of the adsorbent surface is positively charged and becomes negatively charged at pH greater than pH_{ZPC} ⁵. As the pH_{ZPC} of the modified cellulose surface is determined to be 7.4, anionic arsenic is expected to be preferably adsorbed to the positively charged surface of the adsorbent by electrostatic attraction. The stability study of As^{V} species indicates the existence of H_3AsO_4 at $\text{pH} < 2$, H_2AsO_4^- at $\text{pH} 2-7$, HASO_4^{2-} at $\text{pH} 7-11$ and AsO_4^{3-} at $\text{pH} > 12$ ⁶. Therefore, among the different As^{V} species H_2AsO_4^- is thought to be preferably adsorbed at the solution pH. At higher pH, beyond pH_{ZPC} , as the surface becomes negatively charged the arsenate species are repelled effecting lesser adsorption. The behavior of As^{III} species, when compared with As^{V} , indicates that its adsorption was very poor in the pH up to 7.1 and then increases with increase of solution pH above 9. Thus, in the natural pH of ground water As^{III} and As^{V} could be separated by adsorption on the prepared adsorbent. The effect of several major anions viz. Cl^- , NO_3^- , AsO_3^{3-} , PO_4^{3-} , SiO_3^{2-} , MoO_4^{2-} , VO_4^{2-} , SO_4^{2-} on the removal of As^{V} was tested in the spiked solution kept at a natural pH of ground water. Chloride and nitrate show no effect on the removal extent of As^{V} . Presence of other tested anions decrease the re-

moval in different extent and follows the order : $\text{PO}_4^{3-} > \text{MoO}_4^{2-} > \text{VO}_4^{2-} > \text{SiO}_3^{2-} > \text{SO}_4^{2-} > \text{AsO}_3^{3-} > \text{Cl}^- \approx \text{NO}_3^-$ as shown in the Fig. 2.

Fig. 2. Role of foreign ion on extent of extraction.

Analysis of equilibrium data :

The sorption isotherm expresses the specific relation between the concentration of solute and its degree of accumulation onto adsorbent surface at constant temperature. In order to select a model that gives the best description of the experimental results, the data were fitted to different isotherm viz. Langmuir, Freundlich and Langmuir-Freundlich model.

The Langmuir model can be described by the eq. (1),

$$C_e/q_e = 1/Qb + C_e/Q \quad (1)$$

where, q_e (mg g^{-1}) and C_e (mg dm^{-3}) are the amount of solute on the adsorbent surface and the solute concentration in solution at equilibrium, respectively. The constant b represents the affinity between solute and adsorbent and Q is the maximum amount adsorbed on surface. A plot of C_e/q_e against C_e yields a straight line with a slope of $1/Q$ and intercept of $1/Qb$.

The linear form of the Freundlich isotherm model is expressed as follows :

$$\ln q_e = \ln K_f + 1/n \ln C_e \quad (2)$$

where, K_f is the Freundlich constant and $1/n$ is related to adsorption intensity. In contrast to the Langmuir model it does not show a saturation of adsorbent surface and the amount of solute adsorbed assumes to increase indefinitely with its concentration in solution. It was found that adsorption energy is reciprocal to the degree of surface coverage. A straight line is obtained from the plot of $\ln q_e$ against $\ln C_e$. The slope gives the value of $1/n$ and the intercept gives $\ln K_f$.

Langmuir-Freundlich (Sips) isotherm :

The Langmuir-Freundlich isotherm is simple generalization of both the isotherms. Derived by Sips⁷ it considers adsorption energy ranging from 0 to ∞. In its linear form it is expressed as :

$$C_e^r/q_e = 1/Qb^r + C_e^r/Q \quad (3)$$

where, the parameters Q and b has the same significance as in the Langmuir isotherm and r is the power constant. The above model with three fitting constants much better describes the adsorption including adsorption binding interactions among adsorbing compounds. The isotherm constants Q and b can be evaluated from the plot of C_e^r/q_e against C_e^r as in the case of Langmuir model. For independent non interacting adsorption sites corresponding to the Langmuir model, the value r is 1. When $r > 1$, positive cooperativity is assumed, while when $0 < r < 1$ negative adsorption cooperativity can be expected. The isotherm constants are shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Evaluation of isotherm constants

Isotherm	Characteristic	Constant parameter		
		$Q \cdot 10^2$	b	r
Langmuir	Two	(mg g ⁻¹)	(dm ³ g ⁻¹)	
	parameters model	14.14	1.52	
Freundlich	Two	$1/n$	$K_f \cdot 10^2$	
	parameters model		(dm ³ g ⁻¹)	
L-F		0.5832	0.102	
	Three	$Q \cdot 10^2$	b	r
	parameters model	(mg g ⁻¹)	(dm ³ g ⁻¹)	
		18.18	0.955	0.752

The reliability of the isotherm models was assessed by comparing the experimental (C_{exp} , q_{exp}) and the model values (C_{cal} , q_{cal}) obtained from different isotherms. The traditional approach for determining the best fit isotherm model is the linear regression of the whole concentration range and the evaluation of the regression coefficient (R^2) value. But due to the inherent bias in linearization it is essential to find out the standard error of estimate (SE) obtained by minimizing the respective error function across the desired concentration. Moreover, in order to minimize the discrepancies between model prediction and experimental data chi square (χ^2) analysis is found effective in different concentration regions⁸. The χ^2 value is represented as,

$$\chi^2 = \sum [(q_{exp} - q_{cal})^2 / q_{cal}] \quad (4)$$

where, q_{exp} and q_{cal} are the experimental and model value of solute adsorbed at equilibrium. The characteristic parameters for isotherm validity are presented in Table 2. It is observed that for Langmuir-Freundlich model the value

Table 2. Evaluation of statistical parameters

Isotherm	Statistical parameter		
	R^2	SE	χ^2
Langmuir	0.9924	0.2569	4.47×10^{-4}
Freundlich	0.9972	0.0432	1.25×10^{-4}
L-F	1.000	0.0039	1.17×10^{-8}

of R^2 is higher while the values of both SE and χ^2 are smaller compared to the Langmuir and the Freundlich model. Thus the Langmuir-Freundlich model is best suited for the present As^V-adsorbent system.

Arsenic solution of different concentrations was subjected to cyclic voltammetric study and the calibration curve was prepared for analysis of the specified arsenic species in the experimental solution.

The free energy change at three different temperatures was calculated and found to be negative for all the cases. Both the enthalpy change (8.45 k Cal/mol) and entropy change (38.2 Cal/mol) were found to be positive. The process is therefore, thermodynamically spontaneous, endothermic and feasible.

Experimental

All the reagents were of AnalaR grade. Stock arsenic solution (10 mg dm⁻³) was prepared by dissolving 41.602 mg of Na₂HAsO₄·7H₂O in triple distilled water and volume made upto 1000 cm³. The pH measurement was done with Systronics pH meter and the arsenic measurement was performed with a flame atomic absorption spectrometry (Varian 1407). The oxidation state of arsenic was evaluated from voltammetric experiment (Electrochemical analyser, 600C, CH Instrumenta, USA).

Preparation of the solid phase extractant :

The extractant was prepared by mixing cellulose powder with a known concentration of FeCl₃ and alkali solution in definite proportion with vigorous stirring. The mixture was sonicated in a sonication bath with controlled heating for two hours. The mixture was then filtered, washed with triple distilled water, air dried and finally oven dried.

Adsorption procedure :

Desired amount of the prepared substrate is shaken with known concentration of arsenic until the equilibrium is attained. A definite volume of solution is withdrawn after specified time intervals. The sample was filtered through 0.45 µm cellulose acetate filter paper and amount of arsenic in the filtrate is determined through AAS measurement. The state of the arsenic in the residual solution was estimated from voltammogram. The amount of arsenic retained on the substrate (N_f) was determined by the following equation .

$$N_f = (X - Y)/Z \quad (5)$$

where, Y is the amount of arsenic remained in solution after equilibrium, X is the initial amount of arsenic added for adsorption and Z is the amount of the substrate taken.

Conclusion :

The feasibility study indicates that the process is effective. The easy operation and cost effectiveness make it a viable one. The applicability of the process in preconcentration and removal of arsenic from various matrices is under progress.

Acknowledgement

The authors sincerely acknowledge DST-FIST, UGC-SAP and BRNS-DAE, Government of India for support

References

- 1 M Sarkar, M Das and P K Datta, *Indust Eng Chem Res*, 2002, **41**, 6745
- 2 Mitah Sarkar, Sucharita Manna and Partha Pratim Pramanik *J Indian Chem Soc*, 2008, **85**, 1130
- 3 D Klemm, H P Schmauder and T Heinze, "Cellulose in Polysaccharides II Polysaccharides from Eukaryotes", eds S De Baets, E J Vandamme and A Steinbuechel, Vol 6, Wiley-VCR, Weinheim, 2002, pp 275
- 4 D W O'Connell, C Birkinshaw and T F O'Dwyer, *Bioresource Technology*, 2008, **99**, 6709
- 5 M Sarkar and P K Acharya, *Waste Management*, 2006, **26**, 559
- 6 M M Ghosh and J R Yuan, *Environ Prog*, 1987, **6**, 150
- 7 R Sips, *J Chem Phys*, 1950, **18**, 1024
- 8 G L Gore, "Statistical Methods in Chemical Experiments", Interscience Publishers, Inc, New York, 1962